

Potential Antithyroid Agents—III : N-Arylformamidino-N-Arylthiocarbamides

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Since thioureylene linkage of drugs exhibit certain desired effects required by an antithyroid drug, various N-arylformamidino-N-arylthiocarbamides have been synthesised by the condensation of different arylocyanamides with appropriate thiocarbamides in search of some specific antithyroid agent. The preliminary pharmacological investigations of some of the title compounds showed promising results.

HIGHLY active antithyroid substances contain thiourea moieties NHCSNH, capable of being easily oxidised; the suggestion has been made that the interference with thyroxine synthesis is by a direct reaction between I_2 and SH (formed by enolization) forming a disulphide¹⁻⁴. The present communication deals with the synthesis and pharmacological studies of some N-arylformamidino-N-arylthiocarbamide hydrochlorides. The synthesis has been effected by the condensation of different arylocyanamide hydrochlorides(I) with related thiocarbamides(II) respectively. Although we failed to isolate the monosulphide(III), this intermediate stage has been confirmed by many workers⁴⁻⁹.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets and Perkin-Elmer 720 infracord spectrophotometer; bands reported were at least of medium intensity. The results of elemental analyses were satisfactory.

N-Phenylformamidino-*N*-*p*-methoxyphenylthiocarbamide hydrochloride: Equimolar quantities of phenylcyanamide⁹ (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) in dry ether solution and *N*-*p*-methoxyphenylthiocarbamide (1.48 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone were mixed and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed through

Precursors(I) were obtained by the desulphurisation of related thioureas with lead hydroxide and converting them into related hydrochlorides⁹. Thiocarbamides(II) reacts with (I) to yield the corresponding compounds(IV). They are all white crystalline compounds and are soluble in polar solvents. These compounds decompose during crystallisation and hence purification was achieved by repeated washings with several solvents.

the mixture for 10 minutes. A colourless crystalline product separated out in good yield. It could not be crystallised as it decomposed on boiling. It could be desulphided with alkaline plumbite solution, 3.0 g (90%), m.p. 132°. Anal. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₇CIN₄OS : N, 16.64; S, 9.50%. Found : N, 16.58; S, 9.45%.

By adopting a similar procedure, several N-arylformamidino-N-arylthiocarbamides were synthesised

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TABLE 1—N-ARYLFORMAMIDINO-N-ARYLTHIOCARBAMIDE HYDROCHLORIDES

Sl. No.	R'	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis%	
						Calcd.	Found
1.	4-OCH ₃	H	90	132	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS	N 16.64	16.58
2.	"	2-CH ₃	82	150	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ OS	S 9.50	9.45
3.	"	3-CH ₃	80	142	"	N 15.97	15.90
4.	"	4-CH ₃	84	156	"	S 9.14	9.10
5.	"	2-OCH ₃	85	128	"	N 15.97	15.92
6.	"	4-OCH ₃	80	146	"	S 9.14	9.12
7.	"	2-Cl	72	162	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	N 15.97	15.90
8.	"	3-Cl	74	124	"	S 9.14	9.11
9.	"	4-Cl	82	186	"	N 15.27	15.22
10.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	70	141	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	S 8.73	8.68
11.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	80	120	"	N 15.27	15.20
12.	"	2-CH ₃	72	118	"	S 8.73	8.70
13.	"	3-CH ₃	70	130	"	N 15.09	15.00
14.	"	4-CH ₃	74	145	"	S 8.62	8.54
15.	"	2-OCH ₃	71	152	"	N 15.09	15.02
16.	"	4-OCH ₃	75	164	"	S 8.62	8.50
17.	"	2-Cl	78	184	"	N 15.09	14.98
18.	"	3-Cl	68	128	"	S 8.62	8.52
19.	"	4-Cl	74	189	"	N 14.71	14.62
20.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	80	141	"	S 8.41	8.30
						N 15.97	15.85
						S 9.14	9.06
						N 15.37	15.24
						S 8.76	8.71
						N 15.37	15.28
						S 8.76	8.68
						N 15.37	15.22
						S 8.76	8.65
						N 14.71	14.65
						S 8.41	8.32
						N 14.71	14.62
						S 8.41	8.36
						N 14.54	14.50
						S 8.31	8.28
						N 14.54	14.48
						S 8.31	8.26
						N 14.54	14.52
						S 8.31	8.25
						N 14.19	14.10
						S 8.11	8.02

(Table 1). These N-arylformamidino-N-arylthiocarbamide hydrochlorides were characterised by elemental analyses and presence of characteristic bands N=C=S (1515 cm⁻¹), C=N (1630 cm⁻¹) and substituted benzene ring (775 cm⁻¹) in the ir spectra of these compounds.

Pharmacological Screening¹⁰⁻¹⁴: All compounds were dissolved in saline for injection. Thiouracil was dissolved with heating to 55°. Compounds Nos. 5,6,15, 16 were only partially soluble in saline, ethanol or ammonium hydroxide and was therefore injected as a suspension in saline. All compounds were assayed at concentrations equimolar to and ten times equimolar to 0.5 mg of thiouracil (3.9 μ moles) and the biological effect was almost the same at both doses. Table 2 summarises the screening observations made with these compounds.

TABLE 2—PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF N-ARYLFORMAMIDINO-N-ARYLTHIOCARBAMIDES HYDROCHLORIDES AS ANTITHYROID DRUGS IN INTACT RATS

Compounds	Thyroid radioactivity, dpm ± std. error			Approximate activity (thiouracil = 1.0)
	¹³¹ I uptake	PB ¹³¹ I	Inorganic ¹³¹ I	
Blank	8478 ± 50	7196 ± 14	1238 ± 28	—
Thiouracil	4463 ± 62	3322 ± 30	620 ± 18	1.0
1.	4782 ± 15	4043 ± 14	638 ± 18	<1
2.	5194 ± 18	4458 ± 17	675 ± 12	<1
3.	5209 ± 12	4384 ± 16	735 ± 15	<1
4.	5017 ± 19	4221 ± 13	710 ± 16	<1
5.	4625 ± 13	3892 ± 16	651 ± 10	<1
6.	4510 ± 12	3738 ± 20	689 ± 17	<1
7.	4259 ± 16	3415 ± 14	758 ± 20	>1
8.	4112 ± 10	3389 ± 10	668 ± 16	>1
9.	4147 ± 15	3324 ± 18	746 ± 11	>1
10.	4472 ± 12	3582 ± 15	806 ± 19	≈1

(Table 2 Contd.)

11.	4481 ± 12	3676 ± 17	786 ± 15	<1
12.	4728 ± 18	3881 ± 14	788 ± 12	<1
13.	4689 ± 17	3798 ± 12	820 ± 14	≤1
14.	4572 ± 13	3721 ± 22	776 ± 20	≤1
15.	4266 ± 17	3508 ± 15	693 ± 22	≤1
16.	4297 ± 19	3482 ± 18	739 ± 11	≤1
17.	4108 ± 14	3315 ± 18	710 ± 16	>1
18.	4100 ± 16	3288 ± 12	759 ± 18	>1
19.	4087 ± 13	3241 ± 16	766 ± 12	>1
20.	4417 ± 20	3567 ± 20	781 ± 13	≤1

All compounds have antithyroid effect upto some extent and appear to inhibit incorporation of I_2 in a manner similar to thiouracil. Compounds 7-9, 17-19 appear to be slightly more potent than thiouracil.

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